

The Reality Of The Training Courses Provided To English Teachers Using Electronic Distance Learning Instruments During Corona Pandemic, From Their Point Of View

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Abstract

This study identified the reality of the training courses provided to English teachers using e-learning distance instruments during the Coronavirus pandemic. It used a quantitative approach and its sample was 75 English teachers who were chosen randomly from the public schools in the university district in Amman, Jordan. A questionnaire tool was used to collect data, and a statistical package for the social science (SPSS) was the analysis tool. The findings of the study are (i) the reality of the training courses provided to English teachers using e-learning instruments came at the level of (positive average) with arithmetic mean (3.54), (ii) the obstacles facing English teachers in e-learning came at the degree of (Medium) and with arithmetic mean (3.45), (iii) the importance of holding courses and workshops for teachers and students to develop their attitudes towards e-learning and its instruments, (iv) and little attention was paid to the provision of devices and techniques used in e-learning to include all schools.

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Introduction

Education is the basic pillar used to distinguish society from others as well as improves it (Baker, 2020) where a teacher plays an important role in the success of the educational process. Therefore, the successful ministry of education must devote its utmost efforts to develop his\ her knowledge and skills to cope with the new technology (Jonker, März, & Voogt, 2018). This needs designing an outstanding profound plan to implement a training course for teachers (Vykhreshch, et al, 2020) which has to be designed to eliminate the negative points in the previous course, and meet the educational needs. The design of these courses also depends on formal and non-formal education, life skills, and efforts which are devoted to develop and advance the educational process and achieve equality in education between its members (Samady, 2007).

The aim of holding training courses for the teachers is to raise the level of their academic performance by enriching their knowledge, increasing their capacity for innovation and creativity, enhancing their experiences, developing their skills, and providing them with methods of solving problems (Alaa'Shdefat, & Abdullah, 2020). These courses contribute to exploring good competencies of the teachers which can be used in many areas such as participation in developing curricula, production of educational aids, raising the spirits with their participation in opinion and taking their suggestions, avoiding and reducing mistakes in the performance of their work as possible, and avoiding wasting time, money and efforts.

At the same point, Asrar-ul-Haq, Anwar and Hassan (2017) indicate that the teacher deals with several heterogeneous psychological, cultural, and organizational variables while performing his\ her work in the classroom. Thus, he\ she needs to know how to face them. This confirms the importance of implementing training programs for teachers which support their abilities and skills.

From this standpoint, many countries have tended to expand the use of electronic training to develop their teachers professionally and benefit from the outputs of modern information technology and its instruments in training (Sun & Medaglia, 2019 ; Islahi, 2019). In Germany, electronic training for teachers is widely used and through which good results are achieved in the field of professional development for teachers (Bond, Zawacki-Richter, & Nichols, 2019).. In Canada, e-teacher training is a common method used in various Canadian provinces, which aims to provide teachers with everything in the field of professional development for teachers and to provide them with renewed professional experiences (Rehn, Maor, & McConney, 2018).

The ministry of education in Jordan is constantly striving to develop educational curricula and this requires providing training programs for teachers to deal with the new curricula which focuses on e- learning (Al-Shboul , 2013). In fact, e-learning becomes an inevitable issue in the light of the Corona virus pandemic. It is dangerous to follow the traditional method of education, which can lead to health disasters. Therefore,

governments have tended to develop e-learning and to qualify teachers for this type of education, Unfortunately, the academic outputs are still unsatisfactory (Bozkurt et al, 2020). There is a constant need to have a qualitative leap in improving their performance through holding some specialized courses including English which is the focus of this article especially in the field of E-learning. Despite the large studies on the online learning, few studies focus on the training of English teachers via online .

This study examines the obstacles that English teachers encounter during the training programs and identifies the reality of the training courses provided to English teachers using e-learning distance instruments during the Coronavirus pandemic. The findings of this study may help the Ministry of Education determine the training needs of English teachers, it also contributes to reforming the training course for teachers, and it draws the researchers' attention to conducting similar studies on other subjects.

1. Literature reviews

The previous studies focus on the influence of coronavirus on education, and e-learning, and face to face education. For example, the study of Palitha, Chiara, Ming and Libby (2007) deals with the effectiveness of e-learning by integrating podcasts into the English and communication course for undergraduate students at Kingston University. The study finds that the effectiveness of e-learning by employing podcasts to activate the learning process and help students to perform class work, and the students' attitudes towards learning are positive.

Moreover, Alajez, Al-Louh, and Al-Ashqar (2011) conducted a study to identify the reality of training English teacher at secondary schools in Gaza strip, Palestine. The study concludes the followings: The need for teacher training programs that have predetermined goals, the development of the performance of teachers, the need for planning the teacher training programs which bases on the reality of educational science and the various needs of the trainees, the importance of teachers' participation in all program operations, including planning and participation in implementation, the training courses should be suitable to teachers and relevant to the different teachers' qualifications and experiences, and the creation of optional activities, which motivate the teachers to attend training programs and address their needs and problems. While, Gumbo, Mankato, and Helene (2012) evaluate the impact of training on e-learning for teachers in South Africa. The main finding of the study confirms the importance of continuous training for teachers before and during using modern technology in education.

In contrast, Ahmad (2015) studies the effect of using e-learning contracts on the readiness for self-organized learning between English students. The study concludes the effectiveness of e-learning contracts in improving readiness for self-organized learning which was reflected in the students' performance in English language skills. It recommends expanding the employment of electronic learning contracts in teaching English. Furthermore, a study conducted by Bashir (2019) aims at modelling the interaction of e-learning, learner satisfaction and intentions of continuous learning in Ugandan higher education institutions. The results reveal that the e-learning interaction consists of a three-factor structure: the learner interface, the feedback interaction, in addition to the learning content. At the same point, in his study, Aljaser (2019) also identifies the effectiveness of the e-learning environment in developing academic achievement, the trend towards learning English between the fifth-grade students. The results of the study show statistically significant differences in favour of the experimental group in both the post-achievement test and the measure of the trend towards learning English

On the other hand, Sahu (2020) conducts a study aimed at knowing the impact of closing the gates of the universities in front of the students due to the Coronavirus (COVID-19) on the education and mental health of students and faculty. The findings of the study show that (i) universities should implement laws to stop the spread of the virus, (ii) students and staff should receive regular information through e-mail, (iii) the health and safety of students and staff must take a top priority, (iv) counseling services must be available to support students' mental health, (v) authorities should take responsibility for providing food and housing for international students, (vi) and faculty should pay careful attention to technology to improve online learning.

Due to the corona virus effect, Yulia (2020) also carries out a study aimed at clarifying ways of the impact of the Coronavirus pandemic on reshaping education in Indonesia. It explains the types and strategies of e-learning that uses to limit the spread of the Corona virus epidemic, and the study also clarifies the advantages and effectiveness of using online learning. The study concludes that there is a high speed of the impact of the Corona epidemic on the education system, and the study proves the importance of using various strategies to increase the smoothness and improvement of online education.

Moreover, in a study conducted by Basilaia and Kvavadze (2020) aim at studying the experience of shifting from education in schools to on line learning during the spread of the Corona virus epidemic in Georgia. The findings of the study conclude that (i) the transition between traditional education and online education is successful and applicable, (ii) e-learning offers large independence to the students to obtain new skills, (iii) e-learning save time and money for the students and their families. Overall, no study focuses on training English teacher via online, and the main difference between this current study and Alajez, Al-Louh, and

Al-Ashqar (2011) is that the former focuses on online learning while the later focuses on the face to face training.

2. Distance Learning and Online Training

Rather than Internet is used for chatting, reading newspapers, shopping and forums, it is used for educational and cultural purposes. The integration of technology in the educational process has become a global trend (Yulia, 2020). Universities, schools, and academic institutions use internet to facilitate the process of teaching, learning, and communication with their students. E-learning becomes the centre of education in many countries especially during the coronavirus pandemic. This e-learning is defined as education provided on the Internet through the use of electronic technologies (Koumi, 2006). On the other hand, Basilaia and Kvavadze (2020) believe that e-learning is an organized process that aims to achieve educational outcomes using technological means that provide sound, image, films and interaction between the learner, the educational content and activities at the appropriate time. It can be said that e-learning is a process in which education and training are carried out remotely by using electronic means of communication through face-to-face interaction in the online classroom to achieve the planned educational outcomes.

Students, families, and academic institutions prefer e-learning to traditional education for the following reasons, (i), less costs: e-learning saves the costs of creating new classrooms to conduct educational courses and seminars, and saves electricity, water and other materials used in the school. In addition to that, there is no need to go to schools and educational centers, and this will reduce transportation costs, (ii), Learning for all, all individuals, regardless of their age and gender can benefit from the online learning, (iii) flexibility, online learning is not related to a specific time and a place, so individuals can learn at any time from their homes, workplace or restaurants, (iv), short classes, there will be no waste time for chatting and excessive questions. Moreover, students can repeat the lesson many times since it is recorded, (v), the evaluation of the students and exams will be fair without the interference of lecturers.

To reach the optimal objectives of e-learning, many factors should work together, these are: the e-learners, the electronic materials, electronic library, electronic activities, online platform, blended learning. The following figure explains these factors:

Figure1: *factors support distance learning*

3.1 E- Learner

The student must be trained on how to use the computer, the Internet, and the educational platform before starting any online learning otherwise, the desired benefit of education will not be realized. Many teachers

confirmed that some students have failed to deal with online education because of their inability to use the computer and the educational platform.

3.2 Electronic Curriculum

The electronic curriculum is educational content presented in the form of pages through an interactive environment based on web internet, and a set of multimedia (Gamage, 2021).. Hendricson et al (2004) refer electronic curriculum to " computer-based learning, including educational materials available to students by CD or DVD; online courses and web mechanisms used to search the literature" (p.1042)

3.3 Electronic Library

The electronic library contributes to the success of e-learning (Rahman & Mohezar, 2020). Therefore, the ministry of education, universities and academic institutions must have electronic libraries, and these libraries can be used from home instead of visiting them. Students, professors can benefit from these libraries for their research, assignments, activities.

3.4 Educational Platform

Before the invention of the educational platform, education was self-paced by the students themselves. Unfortunately, the students faced many difficulties in understanding the educational material (Smolyaninova, & Trufanov, 2018 ; Olmos-Raya, 2018).. Now, with the educational platform, interactive education becomes available between students and teachers through voice, video and text chats and virtual lectures.

3.5 Blended Learning

It is a type of education that integrates e-learning and face-to-face education together. There are some lectures that should be given online, but they need a practical application at university and school campuses (Hrastinski, 2019 ; Rasheed, Kamsin, & Abdullah, 2020).

E-training is a training process that does not require the presence of the trainer and the trainee in one place. It contributes to enabling the trainee to gain education and benefit from the training process in all its aspects, and it enables trainers to communicate and interact with the trainees. It also allows the trainees to choose their training program in accordance with their work. Online training enables students to overcome various barriers of traditional training such as physical barriers, travel, illness, disability, leaving work and others.

E-training engages in an effective educational system that trains teachers on high mental skills and problem-solving skills by using educational methods in which the teachers rely on themselves (self-learning) according to their abilities and style of learning. Hence, the importance of electronic training has emerged to provide radical solutions to many problems facing teachers to develop them professionally and to meet their technological needs. In addition to that, e-training help teachers develop their skills and professional abilities through access to many resources, programs, research and studies. E-training helps the teachers be aware of new developments in their field of specialization and provides them with many resources that help them know the results of research in the field of professional work and academy. In fact, there are many electronic programs " Interactive Video and Computer Conference Hypermedia Systems, Multimedia Systems, Video Conference systems, and others" (Ahmed, 2004, p.17) that can be used in electronic training to develop the educational process, raise its efficiency, effectiveness and achieve its objectives, electronic professional development for teachers.

3. Methodology

To answer the research questions and achieve its objectives, the researcher used the quantitative approach. To suit the nature of this study that aims at revealing the reality of the training courses provided to English language teachers using distance-learning instruments in light of the Corona pandemic, from their point of view. This study used a quantitative approach for the following reasons. (i) It offers the opportunity to reach large numbers of participants so, the results can be generalized, (ii) the possibility of collecting data rapidly.

5.1 Sampling

The population of study is 4452 English teachers who teach at the public schools in the university district in Amman \ Jordan. Based on the krejice and Morgan table, the sample of the study is 75 teachers who are selected randomly.

Due to coronavirus lockdown, An online form is created on Google form and its link was distributed to the English teachers. The data collecting process was ended in two weeks. The responses of the participants were treated as consent and no one was obligated to answer or abused to answer. According to the ministry of education, this study did not require the endorsement of an ethical body since no important personal information was gathered. The questionnaire survey was distributed online to 95 teachers . Unfortunately, 20 respondents did not submit their answers. Therefore, 75 responses were ready to be analysed.

Table (1) Description of the characteristics of the study sample

Variable	Variable class	No.	Percentage
Gender	Male	33	44
	Female	42	56
Qualification	Bachelor	37	49.33
	Master	23	30.67
	Doctorate	15	20
Experience	Less than 5 years	18	24
	5-10 years	32	42.67
	More than 11 years	25	33.33
Total		75	100.0

5.2 Data Collection

Questionnaire instrument is used to collect data. The instrument consisted of (51) paragraphs, concerns with the reality of the training courses provided to English teachers using electronic distance learning in the light of the Coronavirus pandemic. The statements(1--25) tackle the trends and reality of English teachers towards the use of learning tools. In front of each paragraph, there are five choices, which are arranged from always (1), mostly(2), sometimes (3), rarely (4), never (5), the scale is divided into five categories, which are (less than 2.80: a poor degree of approval; from 2.81 - 4.15: an average degree of approval, higher than 4.16: a high degree of approval). While the statements(1-26) measure obstacles to use electronic learning instruments from the point of view of English teachers, and in front of each paragraph there are five alternatives, which are: (Strongly agree (5), agree (4), neutral (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1). To understand the meanings of the arithmetic means for each of the two scales, the following criterion is adopted: (Less than 2.80: poor approval score, from 2.81 - 4.15: medium approval score, higher than 4.16: high approval score).

5.3 Validity and Reliability of the Study Instrument

The instrument is presented to (8) experienced and specialized arbitrators to know their views on the extent of the consistency, clarity, and comprehensiveness of the questionnaire. This included the statements belonging to the scale as a whole. The questions were modified and formulated based on the arbitrators' recommendation to achieve its apparent validity.

To verify the reliability of the internal consistency of the tool, the Cronbach Alpha coefficient was calculated on a pilot sample similar to the study sample consisting of (15) male and female teachers, and the value of the reliability coefficient of the scale reached (.810), which indicates high stability of the resolution, It is an appropriate value for study purposes.

3.4 Data Analysis

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) is used to analyze the data.

4. Discussion of Results

The results are presented as follows:

1. Results related to the answer to the first question, what is the reality of the training courses provided to English teachers using distance learning instruments in light of the Corona pandemic from their point of view?

To answer this question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the responses of the sample members were calculated, and table (2) shows the results.

Table (2) the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the responses of the sample members towards the reality of the training courses

No.	Items	Mean	S.D	Level
1	Training using e-learning enables me to easily collect information using the Internet..	4.34	1.12	High
2	I feel that training on the use of e-learning increases my motivation towards teaching English.	3.86	1.05	Medium

3	I continuously follow courses and program on e-learning instruments that support teaching English .	3.38	1.20	Medium
4	Presenting your English lessons and activities using the programs you have trained on using e-learning.	3.62	1.11	Medium
5	Involving students in using the e-learning techniques that you trained on because it enhances their various skills.	3.15	1.28	Medium
6	I believe that training on e-learning is one of the best alternatives methods to develop education since it contributes to the spread of knowledge and science.	4.16	0.99	High
7	Training on e-learning motivates me to use e-learning on a permanent and regular basis.	3.38	1.01	Medium
8	Training using e-learning makes students get more academic assignment than reading books, articles and pamphlets through e-learning techniques.	2.65	0.99	low
9	Training via e-learning makes me use e-learning continuously in the educational process.	3.62	1.03	Medium
10	Training using e-learning allows sufficient time for discussion and team work through e-learning techniques.	3.15	1.12	Medium
11	Training allows communication with the educational supervisor electronically through e-learning techniques.	4.17	0.99	High
12	Training via e-learning motivates me to guide students to the educational websites .	3.86	1.05	Medium
13	Training via e-learning makes me satisfied with explaining the English lessons to students.	3.15	1.09	Medium
14	Training via e-learning increases my ability to teach the four English skills.	3.18	1.10	Medium
15	I am satisfied with the advantages that I have got from the training using e-learning.	3.25	1.02	Medium
16	I see that training via e-learning contributes to increasing the learning outcomes in my courses.	3.96	1.08	Medium
17	I am satisfied with the training programs implemented on the e-learning methods.	3.42	0.98	Medium
18	I am satisfied with the annual training plan for the development and implementation of educational technology applications.	2.91	1.01	Medium
19	I feel satisfied that there is a database for trainers and training courses in the field of e-learning.	2.81	0.99	Medium
20	Classrooms equip with e-learning tools help training.	3.64	1.11	Medium
21	I feel satisfied that there is an annual training plan for e-learning programs and systems.	3.18	1.20	Medium
22	Training via e-learning helps me develop courses in an interactive electronic way.	3.82	1.09	Medium
23	I would like to use what I have trained on through e-learning in my courses.	4.21	1.12	High
24	I used the explanatory videos about the e-learning training.	3.94	1.10	Medium
25	The benefit from training courses (face-to-face) is more than e-learning courses.	3.46	0.98	Medium
	Total	3.54		Medium

Table (2) shows that the arithmetic means of the respondents of the study sample to the attitudes and reality of teachers towards e-learning in the training courses ranged from the corresponding level to the average, and with an arithmetic average ranging between (2.81-4.34), and the total score of the tool came at the level of the positive, and with an arithmetic average (3.54) . As the top section of the paragraph was training using e-learning makes me able to collect information using the Internet easily, "then I would like to use what I have been trained on through e-learning in my courses. While I got the paragraph" I feel satisfied with the existence of a database of trainers and training courses in the field of e-learning when needed.

The current study agrees with the study of (Basilaia & Kvavadzai, 2020) which points out that the transition from traditional education to online education was successful, and the system and skills acquired by

teachers, students and school management in the post-epidemic period can be used. It agrees with the results of Aljaser study (2019) that shows there are statistically significant differences in favor of the experimental group in both the post-achievement test and the measure of the trend towards learning the English via e-learning, and with the study of (Gumbo, Mankato, & Helene, 2012), where teachers have benefited greatly from e-learning, and that training teachers on e-learning instruments and techniques is very important before and during the employing of modern technology in education. A study of (Palitha, Chiara, Ming & Libby, 2007), which studies the effectiveness of e-learning by employing podcasts to activate the learning process and help students 'attitudes towards learning are positive. The result also agrees with the study of Ahmad, 2015, which results on the study of the effectiveness of e-learning in improving preparedness, and self-organized learning, which is reflected on students' performance in English skills, and recommended the expansion of employing electronic learning contracts in teaching English.

The results reveal a positive level of the teachers' attitudes towards e-learning. The researcher attributes the result to the teachers' awareness of the requirements of teaching English via e-learning, to their experience in this field facilitates the learning and teaching process, and the spread of technology increases and encourages the use of e-learning, which approves with the positive degree on the importance of e-learning in teaching English, especially after training them continuously and developing their skills through online training courses provided to them during Corona pandemic.

3. Results relate to the answer of the second question: what are the obstacles that English teachers face during the training programs via e-learning instruments in the light of the Coronavirus pandemic?

To answer this question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the responses are calculated, and table (3) shows the results.

Table (3) the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the respondents' responses to the obstacles facing teachers.

No.	Items	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Level
1	The lack of clarity of the objectives of online education and training for teachers.	2.67	1.12	Low
2	Teachers' weakness in using e-learning techniques.	3.62	1.03	Medium
3	Lack of direct interaction between teacher and students.	3.38	1.19	Medium
4	There is a weakness in teacher training on e-learning techniques.	3.15	1.01	Medium
5	Increasing the cost of purchasing the necessary equipment and devices hinders training.	3.62	0.88	Medium
6	Difficulty in implementing some instruments in e-learning	3.82	1.20	Medium
7	The teacher's adherence to traditional teaching methods hinders on line training.	4.36	0.99	High
8	People belief that e-learning is a waste of time.	2.43	0.98	Low
9	The lack of computers to use e-learning.	3.16	1.02	Medium
10	Training time is not enough to use e-learning in teaching English.	2.96	0.67	Medium
11	The ineffectiveness of the available educational devices and technologies in schools.	3.62	0.75	Medium
12	The lack of the encouragement of the educational supervisor for teachers to benefit from e-learning.	3.68	1.21	Medium
13	The weakness of the Internet when using e-learning.	4.17	0.75	Medium
14	The density of scientific and training material in the English curricula hinders the use of e-learning.	3.67	0.60	Medium
15	The lack of knowledge of teachers and students in using e-learning types.	2.92	1.22	Medium
16	A training via e-learning takes a lot of time	3.96	1.04	Medium
17	It is difficult to train scientific material via online.	3.92	0.99	Medium
18	There are explanatory videos on the education ministry's website about e-learning training.	2.45	0.77	Low

19	There are guidelines on the ministry's website about e-learning training	2.90	0.90	Medium
20	Training using e-learning needs a lot of effort .	3.15	1.02	Medium
21	There is a difficulty in applying training on the use of e-learning in educational reality.	3.18	0.98	Medium
22	There are qualified trainers for online training .	3.38	1.02	Medium
23	I need additional information about the e-learning training mechanism.	3.48	1.11	Medium
24	There are financial barriers hinder e-learning training .	3.89	1.04	Medium
25	I need equipment and devices to assist in e-learning training .	3.99	0.99	Medium
26	There are cognitive barriers hinder e-learning training .	3.84	1.06	Medium
Total		3.45		Medium

Table (3) shows that the arithmetic means of the answers to the obstacles facing English teachers ranged from high, medium and weak levels, with an arithmetic average ranging between (2.43-4.36), The mean of all paragraphs is (3.45) and the where the paragraph "The teacher's adherence to traditional teaching methods hinders training using e-learning" occupies the highest mean (4.36) deviation standard(0.99), while the lowest mean (2.43) is the paragraph " People belief that using e-learning is a waste of time" and its standard deviation is (0.98). The current study agrees with the study (Sahu, 2020), which emphasizes the interest in technology precisely to make students' experiences with learning rich and effective. It also agrees with the study (Yulia, 2020), where it indicates that different strategies must be used to increase the smoothness and improvement of education through the Internet.

The results reveal that the obstacles facing English teachers in e-learning from their point of view reach the medium level. The researcher attributes that to (i) the low ability of the teachers to use e-learning or their lack of awareness of the importance of e-learning, (ii), some Academic curricula cannot be covered by e-learning, (iii) the lack of supportive e-learning instruments in some schools, (iv) the weakness of the Internet.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The qualification of teachers where they represent the main element in the educational process. This qualification includes training the teacher according to a modern basis. This study identified the training courses provided to English teachers using online instruments during the Coronavirus pandemic. The sample of the study was the English teacher, the questionnaire was used to collect data, and SPSS was used to analysis data. In order to achieve electronic professional development for teachers through electronic training, the researcher proposes the following: (i) Helping training agencies provide an interactive educational and training environment that attract teachers to employ information technology in training because this contributes to increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of training systems in spreading information awareness, (ii) Establishing an independent administrative body for e-training teachers which is responsible for drawing up the general policy for e-training teachers, developing the necessary plans, and assessing current and future needs, (iii) Establishing an internal web for training the teachers that links e-training centres with the Ministry of Education, schools, teachers' personal computers, and all affiliated training sites, (iv) Designing and creating a website for e-training teachers, so that it is clear and easy to use without complications, (v) Facilitating registration procedures in training programs for teachers wishing to join e-training programs, with the availability of the necessary guarantees, instructions and directives that teachers need in this matter, (vi) Providing teachers with the technician skills in training and dealing well with technical problems that may arise during training program,(vii) Meeting the real training needs of teachers with a focus on the required knowledge and skills that the teachers need which helps them in designing programs, (viii) Updating of training materials continuously and a focus on the practical side of the trainees rather than focusing on the theoretical side, and encouraging trainees to explore, apply and continue training, (ix) familiarizing the teachers with methods of modern electronic evaluation which rely on conducting a continuous evaluation of the teachers, (ix) Including some interactive training activities corresponding to different training methods such as understanding, analysis, application, evaluation, criticism and creativity in the electronic training program, (x) Holding more courses and workshops for teachers and students alike, developing their attitudes towards e-learning, and training them on how to use it, (xi) Paying attention to providing e-learning instruments to include all schools, connecting all schools to the Internet, and providing computers to the students in schools, (xii) Amending the English curriculum to match its application with e-learning, and (xiii) Dissolving all the obstacles to e-learning, in terms of providing Internet and educational platforms.

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